

The Dependence of the Ionisation Potential of Elements on their Electronic Structure.

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Our knowledge of the electronic structure of atoms which is successively due to Rydberg, Bohr, Main-Smith and Stoner, has been recently put in a diagrammatic form by Saha and Ray (*Phys. Zeit.*, 1927, 28, 221). The difference between the Saha scheme and Stoner's is as follows: Stoner has divided the L-level in three $L_{1,1}$, $L_{1,2}$, $L_{1,3}$, the M-level in five sub-groups, etc. Saha and Ray have shown that the division of each of the L_n, M_n, N_n into two sub-groups is more apparent than real, the two sub-levels $L_{n,1}, L_{n,2}$ ought to be united under one single L_n -level instead of being split up. Stoner's scheme has sometimes given rise to certain misconceptions. Some investigators assume that when the M_n -level is filled up, as for example in the transitional groups, either of the $M_{n,1}$ or $M_{n,2}$ sub-level is first filled up to its maximum number of electrons and then the other level begins to be filled up. Saha and Ray have shown that this conception is opposed to the actual structure of the outer shells as revealed by analysis of optical spectra, to account for which we have to assume that the electrons are not divided into two statically distinct sub-levels, but only in one M_n or M_n level. The optical terms are given by the synthesis of the quantum mechanical characteristics of these electrons, according to principles discovered by Russel, Pauli and Heisenberg and worked in full details by Hund (*Zeit. Physik*, 33, 345; 34, 296).

This view is also supported from an examination of the progressive values of the ionisation potential of elements. It can be shown that the ionisation potential of a particular element rises gradually with the number of electrons in the outermost shell. When the

outer shell is completed the ionisation potential reaches a maximum value. The same thing may be said of the radiation potential. Thus when we consider the ionisation potentials of elements from boron to neon, or from aluminum to argon, in which in each case the L_2 -level is being filled up, we find that the curve is uniformly rising and reaching a maximum value in neon and in argon respectively. The same may be said about the transitional group of elements in which the M_2 or the N_2 level is being gradually filled up, with one or two electrons in the N_1 or the O_1 level (see Fig. 2). Here also the curve shows a gradual increase reaching a maximum value when the shell is completed, after which there is a sudden drop when the next shell begins to be filled up. The curve as we take from scandium to nickel shows no maximum at any intermediate point as would be expected if there were a state of separation of electrons in two sub-levels M_1 and M_2 and, if the M_2 -level was filled up after the M_1 -level had received its complete quota of electrons namely four.

We have to explain how these values have been obtained. In some cases, *e.g.*, in H and He, the value of I. P. is known from experimental data. But the results obtained from the electron bombardment method have always to be confirmed by results obtained from spectral classification of the lines of element. In order to be able to grasp the spectral data, I start with the general structure diagram of elements as given by Saha. (The diagram has been taken from the paper of Saha communicated to the *Phys. Zeit.*, "Über Eine Neue Karte des Aufbaus der Atome").

To get the spectral terms, write out the full number of electrons under each level, for example taking Si we have to write 2 under K_1 , 2 under L_1 , 6 under L_2 , 2 under M_1 , then we are left with 2 under M_2 . The constitution of the outer shell is now $2M_2$. To get the optical terms, we have to keep one electron running through the higher levels, and calculate the terms according to the rules given by Pauli, Heisenberg, and worked out by Hund. In this way, let us take all the elements successively.

H, He and Li.—The ionisation potentials are so well known that no discussion is necessary.

Beryllium.—In beryllium the terms expected will be apparent from the structure diagram.

IONISATION POTENTIAL

ELECTRONIC COMPOSITION OF ATOMS.

The sheet explains the formation of elements by the successive bringing in of electrons, K, L, etc. ... denote the successive X-ray levels. The subscript '1' denotes that the electron has been brought in from the zone in orbit having the characteristic of a doublet K-term (K₁). The subscript '2' is in K₂, M₁, ... denote that the electrons under this shell have the characteristics of doublet P-term (P₁, P₂). The full number of electrons in S for X₁, S for X₂, 10 for X₃, 16 for X₄, 22 for X₅, 28 for X₆, 36 for X₇, 46 for X₈, 58 for X₉, 70 for X₁₀, 82 for X₁₁, 94 for X₁₂, 106 for X₁₃, 118 for X₁₄, 130 for X₁₅, 142 for X₁₆, 154 for X₁₇, 166 for X₁₈, 178 for X₁₉, 190 for X₂₀, 202 for X₂₁, 214 for X₂₂, 226 for X₂₃, 238 for X₂₄, 250 for X₂₅, 262 for X₂₆, 274 for X₂₇, 286 for X₂₈, 298 for X₂₉, 310 for X₃₀, 322 for X₃₁, 334 for X₃₂, 346 for X₃₃, 358 for X₃₄, 370 for X₃₅, 382 for X₃₆, 394 for X₃₇, 406 for X₃₈, 418 for X₃₉, 430 for X₄₀, 442 for X₄₁, 454 for X₄₂, 466 for X₄₃, 478 for X₄₄, 490 for X₄₅, 502 for X₄₆, 514 for X₄₇, 526 for X₄₈, 538 for X₄₉, 550 for X₅₀, 562 for X₅₁, 574 for X₅₂, 586 for X₅₃, 598 for X₅₄, 610 for X₅₅, 622 for X₅₆, 634 for X₅₇, 646 for X₅₈, 658 for X₅₉, 670 for X₆₀, 682 for X₆₁, 694 for X₆₂, 706 for X₆₃, 718 for X₆₄, 730 for X₆₅, 742 for X₆₆, 754 for X₆₇, 766 for X₆₈, 778 for X₆₉, 790 for X₇₀, 802 for X₇₁, 814 for X₇₂, 826 for X₇₃, 838 for X₇₄, 850 for X₇₅, 862 for X₇₆, 874 for X₇₇, 886 for X₇₈, 898 for X₇₉, 910 for X₈₀, 922 for X₈₁, 934 for X₈₂, 946 for X₈₃, 958 for X₈₄, 970 for X₈₅, 982 for X₈₆, 994 for X₈₇, 1006 for X₈₈, 1018 for X₈₉, 1030 for X₉₀, 1042 for X₉₁, 1054 for X₉₂, 1066 for X₉₃, 1078 for X₉₄, 1090 for X₉₅, 1102 for X₉₆, 1114 for X₉₇, 1126 for X₉₈, 1138 for X₉₉, 1150 for X₁₀₀.

Fig. 2.

Constitution.	Terms expected.	Terms found.
$2L_1$	1S_0	75074 (?)
L_1L_2	1P_1 3P	$^3P_1 = 58212$ $^1P_1 = 32431$ (?)
L_1M_2	1D_1 3D	$^3D = 18137$

Though the triplet series have been obtained by Bowen and Millikan (*Physical Review*, 28, 256) and the triplet terms 3P and 3S are known, no intercombinations have yet been determined. The above value of the ionisation potential has been obtained on certain assumptions. The ionisation potential cannot be very much different from the value given here, because the strong arc line λ 2348.7 is the line $^1S - ^1P_1$, and 1P comes out to be 32431, i.e., ca $N/2$.

Boron.—The ionisation potential of boron (Bowen and Millikan, *Physical Review*, 1927, 29, 232; also *loc. cit.*) has been calculated from the recent data of Bowen who finds the deepest term 3P_1 , equal to 67546 and the corresponding ionisation potential comes out to be 8.4 volts.

Carbon.—The spectrum of carbon is one of the least known. According to the structure diagram the terms expected are as follows:—

Carbon.

Combination.	Terms expected.	Terms found.
$2L_2$...	$^3P_{0,1,2}$, 1D_2 , 1S_0	No value is accurately known.
L_2M_1 ...	$^3P_{0,1,2}$, 1P_1	

$^3P_{0,1,2}$ have the highest values. Bowen and Millikan (*loc. cit.*) have recently obtained combinations which Bowen interprets as being due to the transition,

$$2L_1, 2L_2 \leftarrow 3L_1, L_2$$

$$(L_2 \leftarrow L_1).$$

If the assignment be correct, the fundamental 3P -terms have the successive differences 16 and 27, so that the line λ 2478 which alone

is obtained with the aid of ordinary spectrographs in the spectrum of carbon, arises either from 1D_2 or 1S_0 state. Assuming that it arises from 1D_2 (which alone gives us strong combinations), we can provisionally put

$$\lambda 2478.8 = {}^1D_2 - {}^1P_1$$

and assign to 1P_1 the value of $N/2^2$, we have ${}^1D_2 = 67799$, the fundamental ${}^3P = {}^1D_2 + 11000$ from analogy with the differences between ${}^3P - {}^1D_2$ terms of other tetravalent elements like Si, Ge, Pb. (See MacLennan, *Trans. Roy. Soc., Canada*, 1926, 20, 362). The I. P. comes out to be 9.7.

The ionisation potential of neutral silicon has not yet been accurately determined, because the higher Rydberg terms have not been traced. According to Fowler (*Phil. Trans.*, 226, 1) the ionisation potential is about 7.5 volts. This can be wrong only by a small amount. Recently MacLennan (*loc. cit.*) has obtained a better value, *viz.*, 7.99 volts.

Nitrogen and Phosphorus.

Both have 3 P-electrons in the outer level.

The series classification of elements with 3P electrons in the outer ring is yet incomplete. According to the structure diagram the fundamental term and the next terms will be as follows:—

Nitrogen.

Combination.	Terms expected.	Terms found.
a) 3 L ₂ ...	${}^4S_{3/2}, {}^2P, {}^2D$	117353 (Hopfield) 39879
b) 2 L ₂ M ₁ ...	${}^4P_{1,1,3}, {}^2D, {}^2S, {}^2P$	${}^2P = 45083$ (Kiess).

Kiess and Kiess (*J. Optical Soc., America*, 1925, 11, 1) have effected some classification in which the final orbit corresponds to (b). Hopfield (*Physical Review*, 1926, 27, 801) recently announces that he has obtained a^2D -term and he calculates from certain rather vague

analogies that $^4S_1 = 14.48$ volts, but the value seems to be a bit too high. No connection seems to have been obtained between Kiess' and Hopfield's terms. The I. P. as given is subject to revision.

In the case of phosphorus, Sur (*Nature*, 1925, 542) has worked out the limiting value of a set of doublet term which can probably be identified with 3P in the fundamental combination. If this view be correct then 4S_1 would have about a value of 72000 corresponding to the ionisation potential of 9 volts. This value is also uncertain.

Oxygen and Sulphur (six-valence electrons).

Values given by Hopfield (*Nature*, 1928, 437) have been adopted as they are apparently quite accurate.

Fluorine and Chlorine (five electrons in P-orbits).

According to the structure diagram the fundamental levels and the higher levels will be as follows.

Fluorine.

Combination.	Terms expected.	Values.
a) $5L_2$...	$^3P_{1,2}$	136900
b) $4L, M_1$...	$^3\bar{P}, ^3\bar{P}, ^3D, ^3S$	$^3\bar{P}_1 = 46747$
	$^3\bar{D}, ^3P, ^3\bar{S}$ } $^3F, ^3D, ^3P$	$^3\bar{P} = ?$
c) $4L, M_2$...	$^3\bar{D}, ^3P, ^3\bar{S}$ } 3P	

Dingle (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1926, 113, 323) and De Bruin (*Zist. Physik*, 39, 869) have observed the quartet and doublet terms corresponding to the combinations (b) and (c). The value assigned by Dingle to $b \ ^3\bar{P}$ is rather arbitrary. Bowen (*Physical Review*, 1927, 29, 231) has recently announced terms corresponding to first combination. The value of the $^3\bar{P}$ terms has been found to be 136900 corresponding to an ionisation potential of 16.9 volts. As regards chlorine Turner (*Physical Review*, 1926, 27, 397) has obtained lines arising from the fundamental 3P level; assigning to the $b \ ^3\bar{P}$ term the approximate value of 8.2 volts which is intermediate between the values of corresponding terms of argon and sulphur, we obtain for its ionisation potential a value of 13.2 volts.

INERT GASES.
Neon and Argon.

Combination.	Terms.	Neon.	Argon.
(X=L, M) 6X ₁	¹ S ₀	173910	127108
5X ₁ Y ₁	³ P ¹ P	89110, 89470, 89887 38040	32557, 33361, 33967 81711
5X ₁ Y ₂	³ D ³ P̄ ³ S	20958—25671	18388—23009
	¹ D ³ P̄ ¹ S	11493—12419	11742—15285
5X ₁ Y ₃	³ F ³ D̄ ³ P	about N/3 ³	about N/3 ³
	¹ F ¹ D̄ ¹ P		

In both these cases, series classification is complete. The fundamental orbit in the case of all the inert gases is ¹S₀ and the next terms are ³P and ¹P₁. The line ¹S₀—¹P₁ and ¹S₀—³P have been obtained by Hertz and Lyman (*Zeit. Physik*, 1926, 31, 469). The combinations and the expected terms are shown in the above table. In the case of neon and argon, ¹P and ³P values are obtained from those given by Paschen (*Ann. Physik*, 60, 405; 63, 201) and Meissner (*Zeit. Physik*, 1926, 39, 172) respectively, who have been able to trace Rydberg sequences. The values given are therefore strictly accurate.

TRANSITIONAL GROUP 1.

Sc to Ni.

The ionisation potential of these elements have been calculated from the following considerations:—

In none of the transitional group, the ionisation potential is yet accurately known, excepting in chromium (MacLennan, National Academy of Sciences, 1926, 12, 726), manganese, (*Ann. Phys. Chem., Madrid*, 1926, 21, 42; see also M.A. Catalan, *Phil. Trans.*, 1922, 223, 127) and molybdenum (*Bull. Bureau of Standards*, Vol. 19, p. 113). The constitution of the outer shell as given in the structure diagram has been obtained from analysis of the optical spectra, which is so far confined to the identification of the fundamental and the next set of terms. Sur has discussed how the Rydberg sequence even in such complicated spectra can be traced, but the task proposed is so laborious that it would take a long time before the full Rydberg sequences are obtained. The values of the ionisation potential as given above have been obtained from various considera-

tions which can be regarded only as approximate, but the actual values cannot differ by more than $\cdot 1$ or $\cdot 2$ volt.

Titanium.—Russel quoted by Payne (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 12, 725) announces recently that the I.P. = 6.8 volts and not 5.8 as originally announced by Kiess and Kiess. Russell's value seems to be a bit higher than what it ought to be. Since the paper has not yet come out, it is not possible to settle the point.

Iron, Cobalt and Nickel.—In case of Fe, Laporte (*Zeit. Physik*, 26, 18) gives the I.P. = 8.15 volts. He has traced two $\text{^}F$ terms which he thinks form a Rydberg sequence. In Co Sur has worked out the Rydberg sequence of $\text{^}F$ terms and the value 8.52 volts seems to be fairly accurate (unpublished work). In Ni, the value has been given by Kichlu, Bechert and Sommer (*Ann. Physik*, 77, 351, 536) from the terms which are supposed to form Rydberg sequence. This value may not be quite accurate.

Atomic Number.	Element.	Ionisation Potential	Remarks.
1	H	13.54	
2	He	24.47	
3	Li	5.37	
4	Be	9.2	Calculated.
5	B	8.4	
6	C	9.7	Calculated.
7	N	14.5	Too high.
8	O	13.56	
9	F	16.9	
10	Ne	21.6	
11	Na	5.18	
12	Mg	7.61	
13	Al	5.96	
14	Si	7.9	
15	P	9.0	Approximate.
16	S	10.3	
17	Cl	13.2	
18	A	15.5	

Atomic Number.	Element.	Ionisation Potential	Remarks.
19	K	4.8	
20	Ca	6.1	
21	Sc	5.4	
22	Ti	6.8	Too high.
23	V	6.5	
24	Cr	6.7	
25	Mn	7.4	
26	Fe	8.2	
27	Co	8.5	
28	Ni	9.0	
29	Cu	7.7	
30	Zn	9.8	
31	Ga	5.97	

Summary and Conclusion.

A preliminary survey has been made of the elements of lower atomic number than Ga (31), but the data are not sufficiently accurate. The spectral classification also has not yet been completed. But from this preliminary survey, the main points raised in this paper have been confirmed, *viz.*, there is a short period of 2 (corresponding to the formation of alkalis, and filling up of X-levels; a period of 6 (corresponding to the formation of the regular group of elements, ending in each case in an inert gas); corresponding to the filling up of X-levels; a period of 10 (corresponding to the formation of the transitional groups I, II, and III and filling up of the X-levels). The ionisation potentials of the Group constituting the rare earths are not known, because their spectral lines have not yet been classified.

In no case above treated, the existence of a subsidiary maximum corresponding to the filling up of an M_{s_2}, M_{s_1} , or N_{s_2}, N_{s_1} sub-level has been traced. It therefore, appears that Stoner's sub-levels are more apparent than real.